

Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication

For Researchers

Trust

Framing and Sensemaking

Power

Values and Emotion

Reflective practice

Underlying Conflicts

Ethical issues

Collaboration

Pre-Crisis

Imminent Crisis

Actual Crisis

Post-Crisis

Introduction

The **Crisis Navigator** is designed as a **strategic resource for diverse science communication stakeholders who communicate science in times of crises**. Rather than offering standardized guidelines (“what to do”), the Crisis Navigator functions as a **sensitising tool** – a conceptual and practical aid that helps communicators *notice, reflect on, and interpret* subtle aspects of their work. Here, the guiding question is: **How can researchers communicate about science when a crisis emerges?**

The present tool is targeted towards **researchers**, whether in academia or industry, who wish to publicly communicate about (their) scientific issues, work, or findings. They are often perceived as “those who are expected to have all the answers”, serving as key providers of empirical evidence to inform decision-making among other stakeholders. This category also comprises higher education students and staff studying science-related degrees, or those involved in research management-related positions.

The Crisis Navigator is structured along four stages: *pre-, imminent, actual, and post-crisis*, taking into account the **evolving dynamics of a crisis**. Ultimately, this Crisis Navigator serves as a guide for researchers to better imagine and anticipate what they are – and could be – up against when communicating science in times of crisis, supporting them to navigate their practice in a more informed and reflective manner.

Challenge: Complexity and uncertainty

GUIDING QUESTION

What are good ways to convey the current state of knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics?

To answer the guiding question, consider:

Information gaps: Identify and monitor what information is available to whom, where and when; and be alert to any gaps that exist or may arise that shape public understanding. It is essential to address these information gaps while avoiding overstating conclusions or creating a false sense of certainty. Researchers may feel pressured to appear fully informed to protect their professional credibility. However, acknowledging what is not known is just as important as communicating what is, potentially fostering trust even amid uncertainty.

Science and evidence: How complex is the science? What is the evidence? Consider presenting nuances and multiple perspectives to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the issue, while acknowledging the limitations of scientific knowledge and the presence of ongoing research or debate. Researchers should convey their research in a way that is transparent, by clearly signaling the information gaps in a language that is understood by the public to make informed decisions.

Voice: Who is able to influence the state of knowledge? Who is seen as credible or trustworthy? Which voices deserve to be acknowledged, heard, and/or given a public platform – and which ones do not? Weigh the pros and cons of giving voice to particular stakeholders and types of knowledge in society, while remaining responsive to audience concerns and providing opportunities for collective exploration of scientific topics.

Clarity and simplicity: The communication of uncertainty and complexity requires clear and concise language that is accessible to a broad audience, and that avoids jargon and technical terms whenever possible. Ideally, this language breaks down concepts into understandable and relatable explanations. Crucially, clear language may also facilitate action in crises.

Underlying conflicts

GUIDING QUESTION

What does each stakeholder need?

Underlying conflicts can stem from differences in values or interests among individuals or groups. They can exert a significant influence on attitudes, behaviors, and interactions. Admitting that researchers are not entirely neutral – being embedded in institutions, disciplines, and funding structures – can help them better understand these dynamics and anticipate stakeholder needs when a crisis does unfold. By adopting inclusive and transparent approaches to communicating science that do not shy away from the question “What is at stake for whom and why?”, researchers can identify where interests diverge and where common ground might be found. This awareness allows them to tailor messages more efficiently, support mutual understanding,

Trust

GUIDING QUESTION

How can researchers enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis?

To enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis, researchers must engage in transparent, consistent, and empathic communication across all crisis phases. However, during the imminent and actual crisis phases, there is often little time or opportunity to build it. This makes the pre- and post-crisis phases especially important for establishing and nurturing trust among stakeholders. The digital public sphere offers opportunities for researchers to engage directly with diverse audiences, promoting openness between science and the public. However, this also demands that researchers act as careful moderators of the contents of their communication in times of crisis, and are mindful of their mode of interaction (one-way “education” vs. two-way communication).

Collaboration

GUIDING QUESTION

How can researchers facilitate constructive exchanges between concerned stakeholders?

Collaboration is vital in research to foster constructed exchanges between stakeholders and provide accurate, coordinated knowledge. Multidisciplinary teamwork not only deepens understanding but also enhances fact-checking and reduces the risk of misinformation. Beyond research, collaboration should extend to the establishment of science communication platforms that can support transdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange among researchers, policymakers, journalists, NGOs, and industry. These platforms could also be used to exchange actionable advice regarding the communication of science. Such collaborations and structures should be established before a crisis hits, as reactive collaborations are often too slow or fragmented to meet demands during crises.

Framing and sensemaking

GUIDING QUESTION

How do different stakeholders frame and make sense of scientific information and science communication?

Whereas framing refers to the way information is presented, sensemaking is about how individuals make sense of the information they receive. Through framing, it is possible as a sender to emphasize certain aspects of a topic while downplaying others. Researchers should remain reflective of both their own framing and that of others, recognizing their potential role as providers of empirical evidence and knowledge. Framing significantly influences how audiences perceive and respond to scientific information; yet, this does not mean that through framing researchers are able to fully control how their audiences make sense of scientific knowledge. Science communication can help different audiences to make sense of scientific information in times of crises by highlighting contradictions and inherent uncertainties, in an easy-to-understand way, and by connecting to different personal situations and social contexts, and by tailoring messages to cultural sensitivities.

Ethical issues

GUIDING QUESTION

How can science communication promote an ethically-sound and responsible crisis response?

Science communication can support responsibility, help prevent misinformation, and support collaborative responses to the challenges at hand. It can promote ethical public engagement by fostering trust through transparency, enabling inclusive communication, empowering individuals with education, highlighting ethical considerations, addressing societal challenges, building partnerships, and embracing cultural sensitivity. An important consideration is that crises inevitably raise moral or ethical concerns and dilemmas when individuals or organizations are faced with conflicting moral principles. For instance, there may be circumstances where full transparency is not feasible or appropriate, such as when revealing certain information could jeopardize public safety or compromise ongoing investigations.

Values and emotions

GUIDING QUESTION

What is the role of values and emotions in science communication – and how do researchers engage with values and emotions productively?

Values and emotions are key to exploring and communicating the complexity of crises and urgent societal problems. The emotions expressed by stakeholders can reveal the values at stake and help frame communication that captures the human dimension of a crisis. However, it is crucial to maintain a balance between attention to emotions and attentiveness to data, facts and evidence – especially when under time pressure. Above all, one cognition proves particularly vital during crises: trust. People rarely evaluate scientific information on evidence alone; they also respond to the emotional cues and relational signals communicators convey, such as empathy, honesty, and openness.

Power

GUIDING QUESTION

Who has the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders and publics?

In science communication, ‘power’ refers to the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders. Researchers, science communication professionals, policymakers, journalists, and the public all hold varying degrees of influence in defining what counts as credible knowledge and whose perspectives prevail. In times of crisis, researchers often feel pressured to provide answers and inform decisions that go beyond their scientific role. To counter this, shared responsibility and clearly distributed roles among stakeholders are essential to ensure accountability and responsiveness. Questions to consider are: What counts as valid knowledge? Who decides? Whose framing prevails? Understanding and navigating these power dynamics is essential for ethical and effective communication about science that fosters informed decision-making, equity, and public trust.

Reflective practice

GUIDING QUESTION

How can researchers continuously learn from, and adapt to, crisis situations?

Once a crisis has passed its peak, it is essential that researchers continue their communication about their science, as the aftermath and long-term impacts are often just as significant as the event itself. Regular reflection on science communication across all crisis stages is equally important. Reflective practice involves critically examining responses in specific situations, recognizing how they are shaped by existing frames of thought, emotions, assumptions and worldviews. Such reflection helps researchers to become aware of their own positions and assumptions, especially regarding tensions and underlying conflicts that may intensify during crises. Sustained, long-term communication of their science can hold both authorities and researchers themselves accountable, empowering publics to remain informed, engaged, and better prepared for future crises. By focussing on the recovery process, researchers can present a more balanced narrative: One that highlights both successes and ongoing challenges.

Deliverable 2.1 Science Communication Rapid Mobilisation Roadmap

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